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Remarks on ditransitive alignment in African languages

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1. Introduction

It is commonly admitted that, in the organization of syntactic role systems, (a) the most basic distinction is the distinction between transitive and intransitive constructions, and (b) the identification of a construction as transitive relies on a prototype provided by the basic construction of syntactically bivalent verbs that describe events involving an agent and a patient in the strictest sense of these words. Constructions in which verbs encoding such events combine with two NPs representing resp. the agent and the patient, and in which the two NPs in question show a maximum of properties typical of core syntactic terms, are by definition transitive, and constructions involving other semantic types of verbs are identified as transitive if and only if they include two nominal terms showing the same morphosyntactic properties as the terms representing the agent and the patient in the prototypical construction.

Ditransitive alignment typology compares the prototypical transitive construction with the construction of semantically trivalent verbs whose argument structure is more or less similar to that of the English verb *give*. A commonly accepted strategy in the study of ditransitive alignment (see in particular *Comrie 2005, Haspelmath 2005a, Haspelmath 2005b, Haspelmath 2006*) is to examine first the relation between the construction of *give* and the prototypical monotransitive construction, and to investigate in a second stage the extension of this construction to verbs whose argument structure departs more or less from the argument structure of *give*.

The argument structure of *give* in its basic meaning consists of a *giver*, a *gift*, and a *recipient*. In all languages, the construction of trivalent verbs encoding this type of event assimilates the giver to the agent of prototypical action verbs, which is not surprising, since this participant quite obviously has more agent-like properties than the gift or the recipient. By contrast, languages show variations in the morphosyntactic treatment of the other two arguments: there is no uniformity, either in the selection of the argument fully assimilated to the patient of prototypical action verbs (henceforth: monotransitive patient), or in the degree of 'obliqueness' of the argument whose behavior is not entirely aligned with that of one of the core terms of the prototypical transitive construction.

For each property characterizing the monotransitive patient, there are three simple types of relationship between the construction of *give* and the prototypical (mono)transitive construction, respectively called *directive/indirective*, *primitive/secundative* and *neutral* alignment in Haspelmath's recent works on ditransitive alignment (see *Haspelmath 2005a, Haspelmath 2005b, Haspelmath 2006*):

– the gift may be the only term in the construction of *give* treated like the monotransitive patient,

– the recipient *may* be the only term in the construction of give treated like the monotransitive patient,

– both the gift and the recipient may be treated like the monotransitive patient.

Of course, more complex configurations can be imagined, at least for certain properties, and the treatment of the recipient and the gift must not necessarily be the same for all properties contributing to the definition of their syntactic status.

The aim of this paper is to compare the diversity observed among African languages in ditransitive alignment with the diversity observed in other parts of the world, and to investigate possible correlations between types of ditransitive alignment and the treatment of beneficiaries on the basis of African language data.

In section 2, I put forward my own version of the general characterization of ditransitive alignment types as discussed in recent typological work. In sections 3 to 8, this typology is confronted with African language data. Section 9 examines the question of a possible correlation between types of ditransitive alignment and the strategies used to encode beneficiaries.

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2. Types of ditransitive alignment

2.1. The hierarchization of the criteria

In the languages of the world, the distinction between syntactic core terms and obliques tends to manifest itself most consistently in NP marking (or *flagging*, according to Haspelmath's recent terminological proposals), i.e. in case contrasts, or in the use of adpositions. A universal principle is that the marking of terms representing arguments need not encode their semantic role, since this role is implicit in the lexical meaning of the verb, whereas the semantic role of satellites must be independently recoverable. Consequently, obliques tend to distinguish themselves from core terms by the use of marked case forms or the presence of adpositions encoding their semantic role.

Therefore, evidence from NP marking can be taken as the first criterion in the characterization of the status of gifts and recipients. According to this criterion, in accordance with *Comrie 2005*, three basic types of ditransitive alignment can be recognized. But the alignment observed in NP marking does not necessarily extend to the other characteristics that contribute to define syntactic roles, and each basic type can be further subdivided. Terms that show the same marking characteristics as the monotransitive patient may differ from it in other respects. Conversely, terms marked differently from the monotransitive patient may share with it some other properties.

Another possible strategy, explored in Haspelmath's recent publications, consists in considering NP marking and argument indexation on a par in the definition of the basic types of ditransitive alignment. But whatever may be the theoretical justification of treating these two types of syntactic role coding properties as equally important in the definition of ditransitive alignment types, this strategy has important practical inconveniences. The point is that the characterization of the indexation properties of NPs representing the gift and the recipient in the construction of *give* is often much more complex than the characterization of their marking properties, and classifying languages according to this criterion often relies on analytical decisions (concerning in particular the status of bound pronouns) whose justification is much less obvious than those concerning NP marking, and which are often controversial, as illustrated by the discussion on the status of Romance pronominal clitics. Moreover, many descriptive grammars of languages that have *P* indexation in the monotransitive constructions do not provide a precise and complete

description of the indexation properties of the NPs representing the recipient and the gift in the construction of *give*.

Consequently, it seems to me preferable to treat indexation properties as a secondary criterion in the definition of types of ditransitive alignment:

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– in constructions recognized as double object constructions on the basis of NP marking, the indexation properties of the NPs representing the recipient and the gift may constitute a criterion of hierarchization of the two objects;

– in constructions recognized as single object constructions on the basis of NP marking, the indexation properties of the NPs representing the recipient and the gift may reveal that a term marked like an oblique shares some properties typical of the monotransitive patient, and consequently is not just an ordinary oblique.

2.2. The three basic types

A first distinction can be drawn between *double object constructions* (henceforth abbreviated as *DOC*) and *single object constructions* (henceforth abbreviated as *SOC*). The term *double object construction* is taken here in a broad sense, and does not imply that the two objects possess every property of the monotransitive patient.

DOCs are defined as constructions in which two participants are represented by non-subject nominal terms showing the same marking or absence of marking as the monotransitive patient: in the case of verbs of giving, this means that, if no case affix or adposition is used to mark the NP representing the monotransitive patient, the NPs representing the gift and the recipient show the same absence of marking, as in English *I gave John a book*; if the monotransitive patient is in a marked case form, or necessarily combines with an adposition, the same case mark or adposition is found with the gift and the recipient, as in the double accusative construction of Panyjima – ex. (1).

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(1) *Panyjima* (Comrie 2005)

a. *Ngunha parnka ngarnarta mantu-yu*
DEM lizard eat.TAM meat-ACC
'That lizard will eat the meat'

b. *Ngatha yukurru-ku mantu-yu yinyanha*
PRO1S dog-ACC meat-ACC give.TAM
'I gave the dog meat'

In SOC of verbs of giving, either the marking of the NP representing the gift coincides with that of the monotransitive patient and the recipient shows a different marking, or the marking of the NP representing the recipient coincides with that of the monotransitive patient and the gift shows a different marking.

The first possibility can be illustrated by the English construction *I gave a book to John*. In ex. (2) & (3), the same type of ditransitive alignment is illustrated in languages in which core term marking follows the accusative type of alignment (Hungarian) and the ergative type of alignment (Avar).

(2) *Hungarian*

- a. *János pénz-t keresett*
János money-ACC earn.TAM.S3S
'János earned money'
- b. *János pénz-t adott Béla-nak*
János money-ACC give.TAM.S3S Béla-DAT
'János gave money to Béla'

(3) *Avar*

- a. *aḥmadi-ca t'ex c'alila*
Ahmad-ERG book read.TAM
'Ahmad will read the book'
- b. *aḥmadi-ca t'ex ḵ'ela jasaλ-e*
Ahmad-ERG book give.TAM girl-DAT
'Ahmad will give the book to the girl'

The second possibility can be illustrated by the English construction *They presented him with a cheque*. In ex. (4), the same type of ditransitive alignment is illustrated in a language in which core term marking follows the ergative type of alignment.

(4) *Chamorro (Comrie 2005)*

- a. *Ha tuge' i kannastra*
PRO3S-ERG weave ABS basket
'He wove the basket'
- b. *Ha na'i i patgon ni leche*
PRO3S-ERG give ABS child OBL milk
'I gave the child milk'

In recent typological literature, *indirect object construction* and *secondary object construction* are often used as general terms for the last two types of ditransitive alignment. However, it seems to me preferable to avoid these terms, since they suggest that the argument whose marking does not coincide with that of the monotransitive patient necessarily shares with it other properties that distinguish it from obliques, which is not always the case. In addition to that, the traditional use of 'indirect object' is characterized by such a confusion between syntactic and semantic roles that using it in a typological framework can only lead to misunderstandings¹. Although it is not a traditional term,

¹ 'Indirect object' is sometimes applied to any nominal term in the construction of a verb that represents an argument, but does not assume a core syntactic role (subject or direct object) – for example, *of this theory* in *What do you think of this theory?*, or *on you* in *I know I can rely on you*. But *oblique argument* is a much better label for this notion, since it clearly refers to the mismatch between the semantic status (*argument vs. satellite*) and the formal treatment (*core vs. oblique*) of such terms, whereas 'indirect object' lends itself to a variety of interpretations that can only be a source of confusions. In another use, 'indirect object' indiscriminately refers to the term representing the recipient in the construction of *give* and other verbs describing the same type of event, whatever its morphosyntactic characteristics. This use is incompatible with

secondary object is not devoid of ambiguities either, since it is also used in the description of DOCs, the secondary object being then defined as a term showing the same marking characteristics as the monotransitive patient, but lacking some objectal properties.

If I had to propose labels for the two types of ditransitive alignment involving SOC, I would like to suggest *dative construction* for SOC in which the term whose marking coincides with that of the monotransitive patient is the gift, and *antidative construction* for SOC in which the term whose marking coincides with that of the monotransitive patient is the recipient. Unfortunately, in the literature on ditransitive alignment, the term 'antidative' has already been used with a different meaning – see *Dryer 1986*. Consequently, in order to avoid any ambiguity, the terms used here will be *SOC with the gift in the role of object* and *SOC with the recipient in the role of object*.

3. Double object constructions

3.1. General remarks

DOCs are extremely common in Africa, and clearly constitute the dominant type of ditransitive alignment in many African language families, in particular among most major branches of the Niger-Congo phylum (Atlantic, Kru, Gur, Kwa, and Benue-Congo) – see Annex.

DOCs are generally more or less asymmetrical, in the sense that, apart from marking, the two objects differ in the extent to which they possess the properties characteristic of the monotransitive patient. One of them (the *full-blown object*) can generally be recognized as possessing every property characteristic of monotransitive patients, whereas the other (the *restricted object*) shows only a limited range of objectal properties. Therefore, subtypes of DOCs involving verbs of giving can be characterized according to the following two criteria:

- the selection of the full-blown object,
- the degree of asymmetry between the two objects (or in other words, the degree of objecthood of the restricted object).

a typological approach to ditransitive alignment, since it implies a confusion between the semantic role of recipient and the morphosyntactic treatment of NPs representing recipients. For example, traditional English grammars use the notion 'indirect object' both for *Peter* in *John gave Peter the book* and for *to Peter* in *John gave the book to Peter*, in spite of the fact that (*to*) *Peter* has different syntactic characteristics in the two constructions:

- in the construction illustrated by *John gave Peter a book*, the NP representing the recipient has the same syntactic properties as the monotransitive patient, and syntactically, there is no reason to add 'indirect' to its characterization as 'object'; in this construction, the problem is rather to characterize the syntactic status of the NP representing the gift, which shares with the object the absence of any explicit marking of its role, but does not possess the syntactic properties typical of objects to the same degree as the NP representing the recipient;

- in the construction illustrated by *John gave a book to Peter*, the NP representing the recipient shows the same marking as the allative complement of motion or transfer verbs, and its behavior does not show particularities that would justify to treat it apart from ordinary obliques and to analyze it as special kind of 'object', if 'object' refers to a syntactic behavior whose prototype is the syntactic behavior of NPs representing the patient in clauses in which a verb coding a typical transitive event combines with two core terms representing respectively an agent and a patient.

but cf. *prepositional object*
object =
(i.e. nonsubject argument)

3.2. The selection of the full-blown object

Outside Africa, DOCs of verbs of giving with a *gift* > *recipient* hierarchy are attested. For example, the Caucasian language Abkhaz has DOCs in which the gift is indexed by the same paradigm of person markers affixed to the verb as the monotransitive patient, whereas the recipient is indexed by a different paradigm of person markers. Similarly, before the development of the preposition *à* in the function of dative marker, Old French had a DOC in which the gift was pronominalized by means of pronominal clitics identical to those used to represent the monotransitive patient, whereas the pronominalization of the recipient used a different set of pronominal clitics (the distinction between these two sets of pronominal clitics being a reflex of the *accusative* vs. *dative* distinction in Latin).

Among African languages, this situation is uncommon, perhaps even non-existent. In some languages (in particular, in languages that have neither object indexation nor passive constructions), it may be difficult to find clear evidence of a hierarchy in DOCs; but within the limits of the documentation I have been able to gather, whenever there is clear evidence of a hierarchy, the argument selected as the full-blown object is invariably the recipient.

3.3. The degree of asymmetry between the two objects

African languages in which verbs of giving have DOCs seem to behave uniformly in selecting the recipient as the full-blown object. By contrast, they show important variations in the extent to which the restricted object (i.e., the NP representing the gift) possesses the properties of the monotransitive patient. They attest situations in which the asymmetry between the two objects is minimal, but also situations in which, apart from its marking characteristics, the restricted object in DOCs has nothing in common with the monotransitive patient.

The *recipient* > *gift* hierarchy in DOCs of verbs of giving often has clear manifestations in the indexing properties of the two objects (in languages that have object indexation) and in their behaviour in passive constructions (in languages that have passive verb forms or periphrases). In principle, any property relevant to the definition of a syntactic role may provide a hierarchization criterion. For example, in Wolof, the two objects in the construction of *jox* 'give' have the same indexation properties, and passive derivation cannot provide evidence of a hierarchy either, since Wolof does not have passive constructions, but the existence of an antipassive form *jox-e* blocking the expression of the recipient is a possible criterion of hierarchization. However, in a typological survey mainly based on published documentation, it is difficult to consider properties other than indexation and passivization, since most descriptions of languages that have DOCs do not provide information on the other aspects of the behaviour of objects in DOCs.

Let us examine the variations in the indexation properties of NPs representing a recipient and a gift in the DOCs of a few Bantu languages.²

Tswana provides a good example of DOCs in which the contrast between the two objects, although not totally absent, is minimal. In the DOC of Tswana, the linear order of the objects is determined by Animacy Hierarchy. The verb can simultaneously incorporate two object markers identical to those used to represent the patient of typical transitive verbs – ex. (5b), and both objects can be promoted to the status of subject of a passive construction – ex. (5c-d). The only manifestation of a hierarchy between the two objects is

² On the DOCs in general, see *Larson 1988*, *Hudson 1992*. On the DOCs in Bantu languages, see in particular *Bresnan & Moshi 1990*, *Moshi 1998*.

that, if both objects are pronominalized, the only possible passive construction is that in which the subject represents the recipient – ex. (5e-f).

(5) *Tswana*

a. *Ke-file bana lobone*
 s1s-give.TAM 2child 1lamp
 'I have given the children the lamp'

also in Siriwati, cf. De Guzman 1987

b. *Ke-lo-ba-file*
 s1s-O3:11-O3:2-give.TAM
 'I have given it to them (the lamp)'

c. *Bana ba-filwe lobone*
 2child s3:2-give.PASS.TAM 1lamp
 'The children have been given the lamp'

d. *Lobone lo-filwe bana*
 1lamp s3:11-give.PASS.TAM 2child
 'The lamp has been given to the children'

e. *Bana ba-lo-filwe*
 2child s3:2-O3:11-give.PASS.TAM
 'The children have been given it'

f. **Lobone lo-ba-filwe*
 1lamp s3:11-O3:2-give.PASS.TAM

*'The lamp has been given them.'

The Atlantic language Wolof – ex. (6) – is another good example of a language with DOCs in which the two objects have identical indexation properties, and can simultaneously be represented by the same object markers attached to the verb.³

(6) *Wolof*

a. *Dama-y jox ganaar gi dugub ji*
 VFOC.S1S-TAM give hen DEF millet DEF
 'I am giving the millet to the hen'

b. *Dama-ko-ko-y jox*
 VFOC.S1S-O3S-O3S-TAM give
 'I am giving it to it'

Southern Sotho (a close relative of Tswana) illustrates a type of DOC in which the restricted object still clearly shows objectal properties, but with an asymmetry between the two objects more marked than in Tswana. In Southern Sotho, both objects can be pronominalized by means of object markers attached to verbs, but a verb cannot incorporate more than one object marker at the same time, and if both objects are

³ In Wolof, DOCs have no strict ordering of the two NPs in object function; by contrast, the ordering of the object markers is strict – see section 3.4 below.

pronominalized, the object marker attached to the verb obligatorily represents the recipient, and the gift must be represented by an independent pronoun in the position of object NPs – ex. (7).

(7) *Southern Sotho*

a. *Ha-ke-fe basadi lefielo*
 NEG-S1S-give 2woman 5broom
 'I do not give the broom to the women'

b. *Ha-ke-ba-fe lefielo*
 NEG-S1S-O3:2-give 5broom
 'I do not give them (the women) the broom'

c. *Ha-ke-le-fe basadi*
 NEG-S1S-O3:5-give 2woman
 'I do not give it (the broom) to the women'

d. *Ha-ke-ba-fe lona it*
 NEG-S1S-O3:2-give 5PRO
 'I do not give it (the broom) to them'

e. **Ha-ke-le-ba-fe*
 **Ha-ke-ba-le-fe*
 **Ha-ke-le-fe lona*

**I do not give them it.*

In Shimaore – ex. (8), in the construction of *give*, object markers identical to those used to represent the monotransitive patient necessarily represent the recipient; the gift can be indexed, but only by means of a third set of pronominal markers (glossed here as O') occupying a different position, at the end of the verb form. Formally similar verbal suffixes (or enclitics) are commonly used in Bantu languages to represent locative arguments; comparative data shows that they result from a relatively recent cliticization process affecting independent pronouns (whereas object markers incorporated to verb forms are reconstructed to Proto-Bantu).

(8) *Shimaore*

a. *Ni-tso-m-zunguha*
 S1S-TAM-O3:1-look for
 'I will look for him/her'

b. *Ni-tso-m-ba Haladi zimarke*
 S1S-TAM-O3:1-give 1Haladi DEF.10money
 'I will give the money to Haladi'

c. *Ni-tso-m-ba-zo*
 S1S-TAM-O3:1-give-O'3:10
 'I will give it to him'

Finally, Swahili illustrates an extreme case of asymmetrical DOC in which, apart from the absence of any adposition or case affix, the NP representing the gift hardly has anything in common with the monotransitive patient. In the construction of the Swahili verb *pa* 'give', the NPs representing the gift and the recipient are neither case marked nor combined with adpositions, but object markers attached to the verb can represent the recipient only, and contrary to Shimaore, Swahili cannot index gifts by means of a special set of pronominal markers either – ex. (9).

(9) *Swahili*

a. *Ni-me-wa-pa watoto chakula*
 S1S-TAM-O3:2-give 2child 7food
 'I have given food to the children'

b. *Ni-me-wa-pa chakula*
 S1S-TAM-O3:2-give 7food
 'I have given food to them'

c. **Ni-me(-wa)-ki-pa*
 S1S-TAM(-O3:2)-O3:7-give

* I have given (them) it.

d. **Ni-me(-wa)-pa-cho*
 S1S-TAM(-O3:2)-give-O'3:7

↑ # How do you say this?

3.4. The linear order of NPs in object function in DOCs

3.4.1. DOCs of verbs of giving with the recipient closer to the verb than the gift

A superficial look at the available documentation on DOCs of verbs of giving in African languages may give the impression of a strong tendency to place the NP representing the recipient closer to the verb than the NP representing the gift. The Bantu examples in the previous section illustrate this tendency, which seems to be particularly widespread among Bantu languages, but is clearly not limited to them. In many Bantu languages (for example, Tswana), any violation of the linear order 'give' – recipient – gift results in agrammaticality. A similar rule is stated in Guéhoun's description of the Lakota variety of the Kru language (Dida) in Bôle-Richard's sketch of the Kwa language (Ébric) and in Toronzoni's description of the Ubangian language (Ngbandi). But languages with different ordering rules are not exceptional, and in the absence of a systematic examination of a representative sample of languages (which would be very difficult to constitute, given the state of the documentation on many African language families), it is difficult to evaluate the exact strength of the tendency to place the recipient closer to the verb than the gift.⁴

⁴ More generally, in any search for generalizations concerning multiple object constructions in African languages, one must always keep in mind that all in-depth studies of this type of construction in African languages concern Eastern Bantu languages, i.e., a group of relatively closely related languages which cannot be expected to be representative of the variety existing at the level of the African continent, or even at the level of the Niger-Congo phylum. In particular, it seems quite obvious that West African languages, in which double object constructions are very common, show a much greater variety of situations than Eastern Bantu languages, but unfortunately, no study on the DOCs of West African languages comparable to those carried on Eastern Bantu languages by several scholars is available for the moment.

3.4.2. DOCs of verbs of giving without a fixed order of the gift and the recipient

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Wolof has DOC of verb of giving in which both orders 'give' – recipient – gift and 'give' – gift – recipient are equally possible. Ex. (6a) above (*Dama-y jox ganaar gi dugub ji* 'I am giving the millet to the hen') can indistinctly be reformulated as *Dama-y jox dugub ji ganaar gi*. The Kwa languages Ega and Fon, the Gur languages Gurma and Ncam (Bassar), and the Kru language Grebo, illustrate the same phenomenon. However, according to Innes 1966, the relative order of the gift and the recipient in the DOC of Grebo is free only "if the sentence could reasonably have only one meaning"; when both the gift and the recipient are humans, the recipient comes first.

3.4.3. DOCs of verbs of giving with the gift closer to the verb than the recipient

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V-T-R
A strict ordering 'give' – gift – recipient can be illustrated by Ewe and this ordering applies including when the recipient is represented by a pronominal clitic, which in that case is enclitic to the NP representing the gift – ex. (10).

(10) Ewe

é-ná tsi-i
s3s-give water-03s
'(S)he gave him/her water'

Other languages for which a fixed order 'give' – gift – recipient has been reported include the Central Sudanic language Kabba (Moser 2005), and the Benue-Congo language Kana (Ikoro 1996).

Among verb-final languages, a DOC with the fixed order recipient – gift – 'give' is attested in the Saharan language Beria (Jakobi & Crass 2004).

3.4.4. Ordering properties of free pronouns and pronominal markers in DOCs

DOCs involving free pronouns frequently (but not always) obey a constraint according to which a pronominal object must stand closer to the verb than an object NP, irrespective of their semantic role. This can be viewed as a tendency of 'light' terms of a construction to be attracted by the head of the construction.

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In languages using bound pronouns, and in which two or more object markers can be attached to the same verb, the greatest care must be taken in looking for generalizations concerning a possible relation between the ordering of object NPs and the ordering of bound object pronouns: the object markers immediately adjacent to the verb stem when two object markers are simultaneously present does not necessarily correspond to the NP standing closer to the verb when two object NPs are simultaneously present.⁵

For example, Tswana is an SVO language in which object markers are prefixed to the verb stem, and in DOCs, the ordering of the object markers is the mirror image of the ordering of the corresponding NPs. In the DOC of the verbs of giving, in which the NP representing the recipient obligatorily precedes the NP representing the gift, this means that the object prefix representing the recipient obligatorily follows the object marker representing the gift, as illustrated by ex. (5a-b) above. But this is not always the case, and it seems that even some varieties of Tswana ignore the rule according to which the order of

⁵ On object marker ordering in general, see Gensler 2003.

the object markers prefixed to the verb is the mirror image of the order of the corresponding NPs.⁶

In fact, even a superficial survey of the possible relations between the ordering of object NPs and object markers in languages having DOCs in which two object markers can simultaneously attach to the same verb reveals a variety of situations that excludes the possibility of any simple generalization, confirming the observations made by *Gensler 2003* on a language sample including languages from various parts of the world. Here again, the only way to discover possible tendencies in this variety would be to carry a systematic examination of a broad sample of languages representative of the genetic diversity of African languages.

In some languages, the ordering of the object markers is less strict than the ordering of the corresponding NPs (see footnote 6 on the Kgatla dialect of Tswana). In some others, it is more strict (see below on Wolof and on Grebo). And when the ordering of the object markers and the ordering of object NPs are equally strict, they may obey different constraints. More generally, it is important to take into consideration that the ordering of object markers may be determined by purely morphological constraints involving only features such as person or number, and ignoring the role of the arguments represented.

this could also be true for NPs (esp. animacy)

For example, as already indicated above, Wolof has DOCs in which the order of the two object NPs is free; by contrast, the ordering of the object markers in Wolof is strict, but it is independent from the roles of the participants they represent, and depends exclusively on the hierarchy *1st/2nd person > 3rd person plural > 3rd person singular*, as illustrated by ex. (11).

(11) *Wolof*

- a. *Dama-y jox xale bi mango yi* ~ *Dama-y jox mango yi xale bi*
 VFOC.S1S-TAM give child DEF mango DEF.PL
 'I am giving the mangoes to the child'
- b. *Dama-y jox xale yi mango bi* ~ *Dama-y jox mango bi xale yi*
 VFOC.S1S-TAM give child DEF.PL mango DEF
 'I am giving the mango to the children'
- c. *Dama-leen-ko-y jox*
 VFOC.S1S-O3P-O3S-TAM give
 'I am giving them to him' OR 'I am giving it to them'
- d. **Dama-ko-leen-di*⁷ *jox*
 VFOC.S1S-O3P-O3S-TAM give

In Grebo (*Innes 1966*), the order of the two object NPs is free if there is no risk of ambiguity, but the recipient precedes the gift if both are human. By contrast, when both objects are pronominalized, the object marker representing the gift always comes first (i.e., adjacent to the verb stem).

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⁶ According to Lutz Marten (p. c.), in the Kgatla dialect of Tswana, as in other dialects, NPs representing recipients must precede NPs representing gifts, but the ordering of the corresponding object markers is free.

⁷ *-di* (following a consonant) and *-y* (following a vowel) are two allomorphs of the same TAM marker.

3.4.5. A remark concerning ordering rules in DOCs

A study of linear order in DOCs limited to verbs of giving may miss some important generalizations, in the sense that, in languages that have a strict order of the object NPs representing a recipient and a gift, this order may be a mere consequence of a more general principle, and therefore must not be stated as a special syntactic rule concerning verbs whose argument frame is similar to that of 'give'.

Tswana is a case in point. In this language, as already illustrated, the order 'give' – recipient – gift is strict, but it follows from a more general principle according to which the order of object NPs in the DOCs of Tswana is primarily governed by Animacy Hierarchy, and only secondarily by semantic roles. The general rule is that:

(a) whenever the referents of the two objects differ in animacy, irrespective of their semantic roles, the object that stands higher in Animacy Hierarchy must precede the other, even if this leads to ambiguities (for example, in the DOCs of Tswana, human objects always precede non-human ones, irrespective of their semantic roles, and a sequence such as *bolaisa monna ntša* 'make kill – man – dog' is ambiguous between 'make the man kill the dog' and 'make the dog kill the man');

(b) when the referents of the two objects intrinsically have the same status according to Animacy Hierarchy (for example, if both of them refer to humans), the order is determined by the animacy properties typically associated with their semantic roles, and the object whose role has stronger affinities with the feature *+animate* must precede the other.

The order 'give' – recipient – gift in the DOC of Tswana verbs of giving must therefore be viewed as a mere application of this general rule.

4. Single object constructions with the gift in the syntactic role of object

4.1. General remarks

This type of ditransitive alignment is clearly dominant in the languages of Europe and Northern and Central Asia (*Haspelmath 2005a, Comrie 2005*). The English construction *John gave Peter a book* is quite unusual for a European language, and in all European languages, SOCs such as English *present somebody with something*, or French *gratifier quelq'un de quelque chose*, are only marginal.⁸

Verbs of giving occurring in SOCs with the gift in the syntactic role of object are also widely attested in some African language families, particularly among those included in the Afroasiatic phylum, in which this type of ditransitive alignment predominates – see Annex.

In most language families included in the Niger-Congo phylum, as already mentioned, DOCs of verbs of giving predominate, but there is an important exception: at least within the limits of my documentation, DOCs are not attested in Mande languages. SOCs of verbs of giving are not rare among Adamawa and Ubangian languages either.

⁸ This is probably the reason why traditional grammars tend to indiscriminately call 'direct object' the NP representing the gift, even in constructions in which this label would be more appropriate for the NP representing the recipient. This is certainly also the reason why early transformational grammar posited a 'dative shift' rule deriving *John gave Peter a book* from *John gave a book to Peter*, i.e. from a construction more consistent with European standards.

In this respect as in many others, the Nilo-Saharan phylum (which is generally considered as particularly problematic as a genetic grouping) shows more variety than Afroasiatic or Niger-Congo, and no obvious generalization emerges from the data I have at my disposal on ditransitive alignment in languages belonging to different branches of Nilo-Saharan.

Dative is a convenient label for the syntactic role used to encode the recipient of verbs of giving in constructions in which the gift is the only term whose marking (or absence of marking) coincides with that of the monotransitive patient.

It is cross-linguistically common that the dative term in this type of ditransitive alignment shows the same marking as allative complements of motion verbs, as illustrated by Kanuri – ex. (12).

(12) *Kanuri* (Cyffer 1991)

a. *Shí-ro kúngóna yíkin*
 PRO3S-DAT money TAM.give.S1S
 'I will give him the money'

b. *Káno-ro lengín*
 Kano-DAT TAM.go.S1S
 'I will travel to Kano'

But SOCs of verbs of giving with the gift in the syntactic role of object are not uniform, and two subtypes can be recognized. In some cases the dative term, i.e. the NP representing the recipient, shows properties (for example, indexation properties) that distinguish it from ordinary obliques, and suggest to recognize a third core syntactic role, for which the label *dative object* is proposed here. But it may also happen that, in such constructions, the dative shows no evidence of being anything else than an ordinary oblique.

4.2. SOCs with the gift in the role of object in which the dative behaves as an ordinary oblique

In Mande languages, SOCs with the gift in the role of object are predominant, and the NP representing the recipient in constructions of this type never seems to show evidence of being anything else than an ordinary oblique. Ex. (13) illustrates the construction of the Mende verb *fé* 'give'. Note that, in Mande languages, the rigid *SOVX* constituent order⁹ results in a clearcut contrast between core terms and obliques.

(13) *Mende* (Innes 1971)

a. *Mbeí yéyá*
 rice buy
 'Buy the rice'

b. *Mbeí ve kpaná we*
 rice give Kpana to

⁹ On the *SOVX* constituent order in Mande languages and in other language families of West Africa, see Creissels 2005.

'Give the rice to Kpana'

The Ubanguian language Banda-Linda (*Cloarec-Heiss 1986*), the Omotic language Maale (*Amha 2001*) and the Cushitic language Oromo (*Ali & Zaborski 1990, Griefenow-Mewis & Bitima 1994*) are other examples of languages with SOCs with the gift in the role of object in which datives in the construction of verbs of giving do not seem to have properties distinguishing them from other obliques.

4.3. Dative objects

In SOCs with the gift in the role of object, the NP representing the recipient may show characteristics that distinguish it from ordinary obliques and justify the recognition of a core syntactic role 'indirect object' (or 'dative object').

Things are particularly clear in languages that have object indexation. In such languages, the fact that datives shows indexation properties similar to those of the monotransitive patient suggests to recognize a core syntactic role 'dative object', whereas the impossibility to index datives can be viewed as the proof that they are ordinary obliques. For example, in Hungarian, the oblique status of dative complements manifests itself in the fact that verbs agree with accusative complements, but not with dative complements. By contrast, Romance languages have systems of pronominal affixes or clitics that justify the introduction of a third core syntactic role *dative object* typically used to encode recipients: in Romance languages, both direct objects and datives can be represented by pronominal affixes or clitics attached to verbs. In addition to that, in the 3rd person, the pronominal affixes or clitics representing datives (French *lui/leur*) are distinct from those representing direct objects (French *le/la/les*), but in the 1st and 2nd person, most Romance languages use the same affixes or clitics for direct objects and datives.

Similarly, among African languages having SOCs with the gift in the role of object, if the monotransitive construction involves some mechanism of object indexation, the observation of argument indexation in the construction of *give* may reveal that the dative term behaves in this respect like a core term, and not like an oblique.

Berber languages have systems of bound pronouns similar to those of Romance languages in that verbs having dative complements may have two bound pronouns attached to them, one for the object and the other for the dative – ex. (14).

(14) *Kabyle (Nait-Zerrad 2001)*

- a. *Yefka weqic aksum i wemcic*
give.S3SM boy meat to cat
'The boy gave the meat to the cat'
- b. *Yefka-t weqic i wemcic*
give.S3SM-O3SM boy to cat
'The boy gave it (the meat) to the cat'
- c. *Yefka-yas weqic aksum*
give.S3SM-D3S boy meat
'The boy gave the meat to it (the cat)'

but this also
applies to some
obliques - Y, en

- d. *Yefka-yas-t weqcic*
 give.S3SM-D3S-O3SM boy
 'The boy gave it (the meat) to it (the cat)'

In Moroccan Arabic, datives are generally pronominalized by means of complex pronominal suffixes, consisting of a first element *-l-* cognate with the dative preposition, and a second element identical with the corresponding object pronoun. But *ʃta* 'give and a few other verbs taking dative complements have the particularity that, when the recipient only is pronominalized, it is represented by the object pronoun, and not by the special dative pronoun – ex. (15).

(15) *Moroccan Arabic (Harrell 1965)*

- a. *ʃtit lə-flus lə-l-xəddam*
 give.S1S DEF-money to-DEF-worker
 'I gave the money to the worker'

money (T) to-worker (R)

- b. *ʃtit-hom-lu*
 give.S1S-O3P¹⁰-D3SM
 'I gave it to him'

gave (T) it (T) to-him (R)

- c. *ʃtit-u lə-flus*
 give.S1S-O3SM DEF-money
 'I gave him the money'

gave-him (R) the money (T)

In Chadic languages, with the notable exception of Hausa, verbs of giving have a SOC with the gift in the role of object, devoid of any overt marking, followed by a preposition phrase representing the recipient, but recipients are most of the time indexed by means of a special set of bound pronouns attached to the verb, as in the Ngamo ex. (16).

(16) *Ngamo (Newman 1982 citing an unpublished manuscript of Schuh)*

- a. *ni on-ko oyu ki Tijani*
 s1s give-PF money to Tijani
 'I gave money to Tijani'

- b. *ni oo-ni-ko oyu*
 s1s give-D3SM-PF money
 'I gave him money'

In several Chadic languages, much in the same way as in Spanish, dative markers representing the recipient tend to be used even in the presence of a co-referent NP in dative role (Newman 1982).

In the Saharan language Kanuri, verb affixes can be used to represent 1st or 2nd person patients. Give, like typical monotransitive verbs, can incorporate a unique object marker, but the object marker incorporated to give represents the dative term encoding the recipient, and not the accusative term encoding the gift¹¹ – ex. (17).

¹⁰ *flus* 'money' is plural.

¹¹ Note that, in Kanuri, the accusative marker *ga* is often optional.

(17) *Kanuri (Cyffer 1991)*

- a. *Shí-ga cítáko*
he-ACC TAM.seize.S1S
'I seized him'
- b. *Nyí-ga njítáko*
you-ACC O2S.TAM.seize.S1S
'I seized you'
- c. *Agógó shí-ro cóko*
watch he-DAT TAM.give.S1S
'I gave him a watch'
- d. *Agógó nyí-ro njóko*
watch you-DAT O2S.TAM.give.S1S
'I gave you a watch'

A similar situation is found in the Ethiosemitic language Amharic with the difference that Amharic has overt verb affixes representing 3rd person objects. In prototypical transitive clauses, Amharic marks definite objects with the accusative suffix *-n*. In the construction of *sätt'ä* 'give', the NP representing the gift takes this suffix in the same conditions as the object of a prototypical transitive clause, whereas the NP representing the recipient combines with the dative/benefactive preposition *lä-*; but when attached to *sätt'ä* 'give', the verb suffixes used to pronominalize the monotransitive patient usually do not represent the gift (that is, the argument showing the same marking as the monotransitive patient), but the recipient (that is, an argument showing a different marking) – ex. (18).

(18) *Amharic (Cohen 1970, Appleyard 1995)*

- a. *Käbbädä-n mätt-u*
Kebede-ACC hit.TAM-S3P
'They hit Kebede'
- b. *(Īssu-n) mätt-u-t*
he-ACC hit.TAM-S3P-O3SM
'They hit him'
- c. *(Īñña-n) mätt-u-n*
we-ACC hit.TAM-S3P-O1P
'They hit us'
- d. *Gänzäb-u-n (lä-ñña) sätt'-u-n*
money-DEF-ACC DAT-we give.TAM-S3P-O1P
'They gave the money to us'

e. *Särräk'-u-t*

steal.TAM-S3P-O3SM

'They stole it'

f. ... *sätt'-u-n*

give.TAM-S3P-O1P

'They gave us (to somebody)' OR 'They gave us (something)'
(the second interpretation being more usual than the first one)

both interpretations

Note that, in Amharic, two object markers cannot co-occur in the same verb form, and that, when both the gift and the recipient are discursively salient referents, the usual treatment of the gift is zero anaphora: in the absence of an object NP, the form quoted as (16f), which includes a unique object marker of 1st person plural, is interpreted as 'They gave it to us'.

The fact that recipients are typically animate, whereas gifts are typically inanimate,¹² may explain at least certain cases of discrepancies between the marking characteristics and the indexation properties of the dative in SOCs with the gift in the role of object. Cross-linguistically, the use of null anaphora is particularly common in relation with inanimate referents, and many languages, at least in certain syntactic conditions, have a more or less systematic contrast between null anaphora for inanimates, and overt anaphora for animates. In such languages, pronouns representing gifts normally do not occur in the construction of verbs of giving. If a mechanism of indexation of the monotransitive patient develops in such conditions, this mechanism will be characterized by null indexation of 3rd person inanimate patients. It is therefore normal that a parallel development affecting verbs of giving gives rise to a mechanism of indexation of the recipient rather than the gift, since in such systems, typical gifts cannot be overtly indexed.

4.4. Problematic cases

Difficulties in identifying a construction as a SOC or DOC may arise in languages in which the same case affix or adposition can occur with monotransitive patients, gifts and recipients, but with a different conditioning.

For example, *Bender 1996* describes for Kunama (currently considered as an isolated language within the Nilo-Saharan phylum) a situation apparently similar to that of Spanish, with a postposition *si* obligatory with recipients, and optional with monotransitive patients and gifts. The fact that monotransitive patients and gifts have in common the possibility to remain unmarked, whereas recipients are obligatorily marked, suggests to recognize a SOC with the gift in the role of object. However, further investigations would be necessary in order to rule out another possible analysis, according to which the obligatoriness of the postposition *si* with recipients could be the mere consequence of a more general principle (perhaps involving Animacy Hierarchy) operating within the frame of a DOC.

yes!

¹² In many languages, there is no difficulty imagining situations in which the usual equivalent of *give* combines with atypical recipients or gifts. For example, constructions such as *They gave me to you (as a slave, a wife, a foster child, etc.)* are often possible. But this is not always the case. Some languages have a total ban on the selection of animate gifts (and consequently, on the selection of 1st or 2nd person gifts) in the construction of the verb constituting the usual equivalent of English *give*. Unfortunately, it is difficult to gather cross-linguistic documentation on such constraints, since most descriptive grammars provide illustrations of verbs of giving with animate recipients and inanimate gifts only, and omit to discuss the acceptability of less common configurations.

5. Single object constructions with the recipient in the role of object

Of the three types of ditransitive alignment identifiable in terms of NP marking, the third one is the less common cross-linguistically. It is sporadically attested as a minor type in many languages, but can be recognized as the dominant type in very few languages only.

In principle, in this type, the term representing the gift may show variations in its degree of obliqueness, in the same way as the dative in the type examined in section 3. But I know of no example of a construction in which a gift marked differently from the monotransitive patient would at the same time distinguish itself from ordinary obliques by possessing some properties otherwise characteristic of core syntactic terms.

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Mende, which has served to illustrate SOC with the gift in the role of object – ex. (13), has another verb semantically equivalent to English *give*, but with a construction in which the recipient is assimilated to the monotransitive patient, and the gift treated as an oblique – ex. (19).

(19) *Mende* (Innes 1971)

- a. *Kpanâ lólí*
Kpana call
'Call Kpana'
- b. *Kpanâ gó a mbeí*
Kpana give with rice
'Give the rice to Kpana'

Bambara is another example of a language having two equivalents of the English verb *give*: *dí* occurs in a SOC with the gift in the role of object, whereas *són* has a SOC with the recipient in the role of object – ex. (20).

(20) *Bambara*

- a. *Modu ye wari di Seku ma*
Modou TAM money give Sékou POSTP
'Modou gave money to Sékou'
- b. *Modu ye Seku sɔn wari la*
Modu TAM Sékou give money POSTP
same meaning: 'Modou gave money to Sékou'

The Benue-Congo language Yoruba is often mentioned one of the few languages in which the usual equivalent of *give* (Yoruba: *fún*) shows this type of alignment – ex. (21).

(21) *Yoruba*

- a. *Ọjọ fún iyá ní owó*
Ojo give mother PREP money
'Ojo gave mother money'

- b. *Òjọ́ fún-un ní owó*
 Ojo give-OM3S PREP money
 'Ojo gave her money'

Within the limits of my documentation, the only other African language in which the usual equivalent of *give* shows this type of alignment is the Khoisan language =Hoan, but this analysis of the construction of *give* in =Hoan can be contested on the basis of the fact that it involves a preposition with some unusual properties. This question is discussed below in section 8.3.2.

6. The *take ... give* construction

In all three basic types discussed in the previous sections, the meaning 'give' is encoded in monoverbal constructions involving three distinct nominal terms representing one of the three participants each. But serializing languages attest a type of constructions departing from this general characterization, in which the verb *give* occurs in a serial construction in which the gift is treated as the complement of a verb whose basic meaning is *take*.

For example, the Kwa language Kposso has two possible constructions of *ká* 'give': a DOC, and a construction of the *take ... give* type – ex. (22).

(22) *Kposso* (Eklo 1987)

- a. *kúmá á-ká kōkó itùkpá*
 Kuma S3S.TAM-give Koku goat
 'Kuma gave Koku a goat'
- b. *kúmá á-jō itùkpá ká kōkó*
 Kuma S3S.TAM-take goat give Koku
 'Kuma gave Koku a goat'

This situation is commonly found in languages that, more generally, have a more or less productive possibility of paraphrasing transitive verbs by means of a serial construction in which the term encoded as the object in the monoverbal transitive construction is not directly linked to the verb from which it receives its semantic role, but to another verb whose basic meaning is 'take', as in ex. (23) from the Kwa language Fon.¹³

(23) *Fon* (Lambert-Brétière 2005)

- a. *é tá lánpù ó*
 s3s light lamp DEF
 'He lit the lamp'
- b. *é só lánpù ó tá*
 s3s take lamp DEF light
 'He lit the lamp'

¹³ On this type of construction in West African languages, see Lord 1993:65-138. Outside Africa, Mandarin Chinese provides an example, documented in written records, of a verb *take* grammaticalizing into a preposition marking NPs in the role of object.

In other words, the *take ... give* construction is typical of serializing languages in which *take* tends to grammaticalize as an accusative marker. The serializing languages of West Africa in which this phenomenon can be observed show a general tendency to avoid constructions with more than two terms directly linked to the same verb, which means that the *take* periphrasis, although possible with bivalent verbs also, is particularly frequent with trivalent verbs of all possible semantic types, and not only with verbs of giving. Ex. (24) from Kposo shows that, in this construction, *take* must not be taken in its literal meaning, and transmits to its object a semantic role belonging to the argument structure of the second verb.

(24) *Kposo (Eklo 1987)*

kúmá á-jǒ ídúnū wà kǒkó
 Kuma S3S.TAM-take house show Koku
 'Kuma showed his house to Koku'

Diachronically, the generalization of this construction could lead to the emergence of a rather strange type of SOC of trivalent verbs, with a term showing the same marking (the preposition resulting from the grammaticalization of *give*) as the monotransitive patient, and another term sharing with the subject the absence of any overt marking.

In most languages that have a *take ... give* construction, it alternates with a DOC. However, in Yoruba, the *take ... give* construction alternates with the SOC with the recipient in the role of object illustrated by ex. (21) above – ex. (25).

(25) *Yoruba*

a. *Òjọ́ fún iyá ní owó*
 Ojo give mother PREP money
 'Ojo gave mother money'

b. *Òjọ́ fí owó fún iyá*
 Ojo take money give mother
 'Ojo gave her money'

I have also one language in my language sample, Kolokuma Ijo, in which this construction seems to be the only possibility. *Williamson 1965* does not explicitly exclude the possibility of a monoverbal construction, but the fact that she discusses valency patterns and valency changes without mentioning the existence of monoverbal construction involving semantically trivalent verbs suggests that such constructions probably do not exist in Kolokuma Ijo.

7. Verbs of giving with alternative constructions

Verbs of giving with constructions of different types may be attested in the same language (see above examples from Mende and Bambara), and it may even occur that a same verb with the meaning 'give' has two alternative constructions. The English verb *give* is a well-known example of this phenomenon, illustrated in this section by the Nilotic language Lango and by Eastern Songhay.

7.1. The case of Lango

In Lango, *mìyò* 'give' has two alternative constructions: a DOC, and a SOC with the gift in the role of object – ex. (26).

(26) *Lango* (Noonan 1992)

a. *lócə̀ òmìyò dákò búk*
man s3s.give.TAM woman book
'The man gave the woman the book'

b. *lócə̀ òmìyò búk bòt dákò*
man s3s.give.TAM book to woman
'The man gave the book to the woman'

Noonan's description of Lango includes a detailed account of the syntactic properties of this verb, and the data provided is particularly interesting to examine in connection with the question of animacy effects in the construction of verbs of giving.

Lango has object indexation by means of verbal suffixes, but the paradigm of object markers can be used for human referents only, and the absence of any overt mention of the object of a transitive verb is interpreted as non-human 3rd person anaphora.

In this context, it is not surprising that, with *mìyò* 'give', object markers suffixed to the verb usually represent the recipient. However, human gifts are possible, and in that case, the only available option is the SOC with the gift in the role of object – ex. (27).

(27) *Lango* (Noonan 1992)

a. *lócə̀ òmìyá búk*
man s3s.give.TAM.O1S book
'The man gave me the book'

b. *lócə̀ òmìyá*
man s3s.give.TAM.O1S
'The man gave it to me'

c. *lócə̀ òmìyé bòtə̀*
man s3s.give.TAM.O3S to.1S
'The man gave him (e. g. a slave) to me'

7.2. The case of Eastern Songhay

In Eastern Songhay, illustrated here by Zarma and Gao Songhay,¹⁴ the *SVOX* constituent order (which is the only possible constituent order in Western Songhay and in Northern Songhay) has a marginal status. For typical transitive verbs, the *SOVX* order is, either the only possible order (in Gao Songhay), or the preferred order (in Zarma). As in Mande languages, no more than one nominal term can be inserted between *S* and *V*. The

¹⁴ On Zarma, see Oumarou Yaro 1993. On Gao Songhay, see Heath 1999.

SOC of *nóó* 'give' with the gift in the role of object illustrated by ex. (28) is consistent with these particularities of Eastern Songhay.

(28) *Zarma (Oumarou Yaro 1993)*

múúsà nà ǰgà mòótàà nóó káyndó sè
 Moussa TAM 3S car.DEF give younger brother.DEF DAT
 'Moussa has given his car to his younger brother'

But a particularity that sharply distinguishes Eastern Songhay from Mande languages (where the rigid *SOVX* constituent order suffers no exception) is the existence of a limited class of semantically bivalent verbs whose second argument must occur in postverbal position, but shows no evidence of an oblique status, as illustrated by ex. (29). Oumarou Yaro argues that the behavioral properties of the second argument of such verbs do not differ from those of the second argument or prototypical transitive verbs, and that consequently this constituent must be recognized as a variety of object.¹⁵ The same analysis is proposed by Heath for Gao Songhay.

(29) *Zarma (Oumarou Yaro 1993)*

- a. *ábdù gá himá bààbò* / **ábdù gá bààbòó himá*
 Abdou TAM resemble father.DEF
 'Abdou resembles his father'
- b. *ábdù gá báá ǎysà* / **ábdù gá ǎysà bá*
 Abdou TAM love Aïssa
 'Abdou loves Aïssa'
- c. *ábdù dí zànkà* / **ábdù nà zànkà dí*
 Abdou see child.PL.DEF
 'Abdou saw the children'

The existence of two possible positions for objects (immediately to the left and immediately to the right of the verb) in Eastern Songhay syntax permits an original type of DOC of verbs of giving competing with the SOC already illustrated by ex. (27). In Gao Songhay, *noo* 'give' can be constructed with the gift encoded as a preverbal object, and the recipient as an oblique, as in ex. (30a), or with the recipient encoded as a preverbal object, and the gift as a postverbal object, as in ex. (30b).

(30) *Gao Songhay (Heath 1999)*

- a. *a na ateyoo noo yane*
 3S TAM tea.DEF give 1S.DAT
 'She gave me the tea'
- b. *a na ey noo ateyoo*

¹⁵ Oumarou Yaro 1993 gives the following list of transitive verbs whose object cannot occur in preverbal position: *máá* 'hear', 'feel', *dí* 'see', *dòóná* 'be accustomed to', *dùù* 'get', 'have', *hín* 'surpass', *himá* 'resemble', *máànù* 'approach', *báá* 'like', *wáání* 'know'.

3S TAM 1S give tea.DEF
 'She gave the tea to me'

7.3. The case of Beria

The Saharan language Beria is a verb-final language in which verbs of giving can occur in a DOC with the fixed order *recipient – gift – 'give'*, or in a SOC with the gift in the role of object in which the preferred order is *gift – recipient – 'give'*. A SOC of verbs of giving with the recipient preceding the gift is possible, but is interpreted as expressing the focalization of the recipient (Jakobi & Crass 2004).

8. Some problematic cases

8.1. Constructions with the recipient treated as a possessive modifier of the gift?

To the best of my knowledge, the recognition of constructions in which the recipient in the construction of *give* is more or less assimilated to a possessive modifier of the gift was first proposed by *Creissels 1979* for the Kwa language Baule and a few other languages spoken in various parts of the world. More recently, similar proposals have been made by other authors (see in particular *Croft 1985, Lehmann & al 2004, Daniel 2006*). In Baule, this analysis is suggested by the following observations:

(a) Baule has a fully productive construction of the *take ... give* type along with a monoverbal construction in which the possible combinations of recipient and gift are limited;

(b) in Baule, genitival dependents are retaken by a pronoun anteposed to their head, and in the monoverbal construction of *give*, the NP in the role of recipient is retaken by a pronoun anteposed to the NP representing the gift exactly in the same way – ex. (31a-b);

(c) the only possible combinations of recipient and gift in the monoverbal construction are those giving rise to sequences that have the appearance of genitival constructions; note in particular the impossibility to dissociate the recipient from the possessor of the gift, contrasting with the absence of similar restrictions in the monoverbal construction of *k/le* 'show' – ex. (31c-e). ? t

(31) *Baule*

a. *màn kòfí (i) bólí*
 give Kofi (3S) goat
 'Give Kofi a goat'

compare with *kòfí (i) bólí nì* 'Kofi's goat' (where *nì* is a definite marker)

b. *màn blā mù bé bólí*
 give woman PL 3P goat
 'Give the women a goat'

compare with *blā mù bé bólí nì* 'The goat of the women' (where *nì* is a definite marker)

c. *klè mí wó suǎ nì* OR *fà wó suǎ nì klè mí*
 show 3s 2s house DEF take 2s house DEF show 3s
 'Show me your house'

d. **màn mí wó bólí nì*
 give 1s 2s goat DEF

e. *fà wó bólí nì màn mí*
 take 2s goat DEF give 1s
 'Give me your goat'

However, a systematic application of constituency tests does not confirm this hypothesis: in focalization, the NPs representing the recipient and the gift clearly behave as two distinct terms in the construction of *give* – ex. (32).

(32) *Baule*

a. *kòfí yé kuàkú à-màn (i) bólí ò*
 Kofi FOC Kouakou TAM-give (3s) goat FOC
 'Kouakou gave KOFI a goat'

b. *bólí yé kuàkú à-màn kòfí ò*
 goat FOC Kouakou TAM-give Kofi FOC
 'Kouakou gave A GOAT to Kofi'

(?): (i) *bé yé ...*

This leaves open the possibility that perhaps, the NPs representing the recipient and the gift in the construction of the Baule verb *man* 'give' are basically two distinct terms in the construction of the verb, but are at the same time, contrary to current assumptions on syntactic structure, in some kind of direct interdependence relation that constrains their possible combinations, when they are adjacent to each other, in the same way as if the recipient were a genitival modifier of the gift.

8.2. Constructions involving atypical prepositions

8.3.1. General observations

In several African languages having *SVO* as their basic constituent order, the construction of *give* involves a word that can be identified as a preposition, since it always precedes NPs, and its presence is syntactically conditioned. But this word has properties somewhat unexpected for prepositions. Ordinary prepositions may have uses in which they transmit to their complement a semantic role assigned by the verb, but they also have uses in which they function as semantic role assigners. By contrast, the atypical prepositions considered in this section are purely syntactic elements that never contribute to the recognition of the semantic role of their complement; this means that their complement is always, either an argument of the verb, or an oblique whose semantic role is, either retrievable from its lexical meaning, ~~either~~ marked independently of the presence of the preposition.

These prepositions have been variously designated as ‘transitive particles’ (Dickens), ‘default prepositions’, ‘multipurpose oblique markers’¹⁶ (Güldeman), or ‘linkers’ (Collins). ‘Transparent prepositions’ would be another possible label.

In the most extreme cases (illustrated below by the Khoisan language Ju|’hoan, the Bantu language Nande, and the Gur language Lamba), these atypical prepositions have additional characteristics distinguishing them from ordinary prepositions:

- they never occur in immediate postverbal position,
- if the term they introduce has the possibility to move to a preverbal position, this movement triggers the deletion of the preposition,
- there is no fixed order of the nominal terms following the verb, which means that, even in the construction of a given verb, the ‘transparent preposition’ may mark any non-subject term (argument or satellite), depending on the linear order of the nominal terms in postverbal position.

a For example, in the Khoisan language Ju|’hoan (Dickens 2005), verbs divide into three classes according to the number of the non-subject terms that can be present without triggering the use of the verbal suffix -a encoding the presence of at least one term outside the valency of the verb in postverbal position: intransitive, transitive, and ditransitive. Independently of the use of this verbal suffix (glossed VE ‘valency-external participant’), postverbal terms are introduced by the preposition kò if and only if they are separated from the verb by another term. Ex. (33) & (34) illustrate this mechanism with the intransitive verb *!ái* ‘die’ and with the transitive verb *||ohm* ‘chop’. Note that, in these examples, there are at most two terms in postverbal position, but the presence of additional terms in postverbal position would require the repetition of *kò* before all postverbal terms not immediately adjacent to the verb.

(33) *Ju|’hoan* (Dickens 2005)

a. *Mí !ú-n!a ’àn !ái*
 1s grand-father die
 ‘My grandfather died’

b. *Mí !ú-n!a ’àn !ái-á |Aotcha*
 1s grand-father die-VE |Aotcha
 ‘My grandfather died at |Aotcha’

c. *Mí !ú-n!a ’àn !ái-á goàq=’àn* OR *Mí !ú-n!a ’àn goàq=’àn !ái*¹⁷
 1s grand-father die-VE yesterday 1s grand-father yesterday die
 ‘My grandfather died yesterday’

d. *Ha !ái-á |Aotcha kò |ámà hè*
 3s die-VE |Aotcha kò today
 ‘He died in |Aotcha today’

¹⁶ This denomination may be appropriate for some languages, but in others it is quite misleading, since in languages with a free ordering of postverbal NPs, these atypical prepositions may be used with the object of typical transitive verbs in the same conditions as with any other postverbal NPs – see in particular ex. (34c).

¹⁷ NPs having a temporal meaning can be placed in preverbal position, in which case the suffix *-a* is not required.

- e. *Ha /áí-á /ámà hè kò /Aotcha*
 3S die-VE today KO |Aotcha
 'He died in |Aotcha today'

(34) *Ju/'hoan (Dickens 2005)*

- a. *Ha kú //ohm !àhn*
 1S IPF chop tree
 'He was chopping the tree'
- b. *Ha kú //ohm-a !àhn kò g/úí*
 1S IPF chop-VE tree KO forest
 'He was chopping the tree in the forest'
- c. *Ha kú //ohm-a g/úí kò !àhn*
 1S IPF chop-VE forest KO tree
 'He was chopping the tree in the forest'

8.3.2. *Atypical prepositions in the construction of give: Ju/'hoan and other Khoisan languages*

In Ju/'hoan, the verb /a'àn 'give' can be followed by two postverbal terms representing the recipient and the gift. According to the general rule, the second one must be introduced by *kò*. The order /a'àn – recipient – *kò* – gift seems to be usual, but /a'àn – gift – *kò* – recipient is also possible, and valency-external terms may even be inserted between the NPs representing arguments, or precede them – ex. (35).

(35) *Ju/'hoan (Baker & Collins 2006)*

- a. *Mi /'an Maria ko ambere ko tzi*
 1S give Maria KO bucket KO outside
 'I give Maria the bucket outside'
- b. *Mi /'an tzi ko Maria ko ambere*
 1S give outside KO Maria KO bucket
- c. *Mi /'an Maria ko tzi ko ambere*
 1S give Maria KO outside KO bucket
- d. *Mi /'an ambere ko Maria ko tzi*
 1S give bucket KO Maria KO outside
- e. *Mi /'an tzi ko ambere ko Maria*
 1S give outside KO bucket KO Maria
- f. *Mi /'an ambere ko tzi ko Maria*
 1S give bucket KO outside KO Maria

In Ju/'hoan, the only evidence of a syntactic role 'object' is that objects do not trigger the use of the verbal suffix -a, whereas obliques do. In the monotransitive construction, the

object does not necessarily precede the obliques, and the use of *kò* does not depend on the *object vs. oblique* distinction, but only on the linear ordering of postverbal terms – see ex. (34) above. In the construction of *give*, both the gift and the recipient share with the monotransitive patient the possibility to be present without triggering the use of the verbal suffix encoding the presence of a valency-external term, and consequently, in spite of the obligatory presence of a preposition, the construction of /a 'àn 'give' in Ju|'hoan must be analysed as a DOC in which the presence *vs.* absence of a preposition is not relevant to the characterization of the term it introduces as aligned on the monotransitive patient or not. Note that (35b) and (35e), in which both the gift and the recipient are introduced by *kò*, are crucial to exclude the analysis of this construction as a SOC in which the gift and the recipient would have equal access to the role of object.

Atypical prepositions functioning as purely syntactic elements that never contribute to the identification of semantic roles constitute a common feature of non-Khoe South African Khoisan languages. However, in the two languages for which I have data, =Hoan (Collins 2003) and N|uu (Collins 2005), contrary to Ju|'hoan *kò*, the transparent preposition behaves in other respects like a 'normal' preposition, and this has important repercussions on the analysis of the construction of *give* in those languages.

=Hoan has a preposition *ki* used in much the same way as Ju|'hoan *kò*, with however the important difference that =Hoan has a fixed ordering of postverbal terms (Collins 2003, Baker & Collins 2006). With monotransitive verbs, the object is obligatorily in immediate postverbal position. With *cu* 'give', the order is obligatorily *cu – recipient – ki – gift*, and the construction can therefore be analysed as a SOC with the recipient in the role of object – ex. (36).

(36) =Hoan (Collins 2003)

Ma 'a cu Jefò ki setinkane
 1S PROG give Jeff KI hand-harp
 'I am giving Jeff the hand-harp'

In the case of N|uu, the transparent preposition *ŋ* does not occur in the construction of *?āa* 'give', and the NP representing the recipient is marked by a special dative suffix *-a*. The only difference with ordinary SOCs with the gift in the role of object is that the recipient in the dative case immediately follows the verb and precedes the gift devoid of any overt marking – ex (37).¹⁸

(37) N|uu (Collins 2005)

Griet ke si ?āa ku-a doŋki-si
 Griet DECL FUT give 3S-DAT tree-SG
 'Griet will give him the donkey'

¹⁸ In this example, the fact that the recipient is represented by a pronoun could be an explanation of this unusual constituent order, since pronouns often show a tendency to stand closer to the verb, irrespective of their role. But Collins 2005 provides examples involving other verbs having the same construction, in which ordinary NPs marked dative occupy the same position.

8.3.3. Atypical prepositions in the construction of *give*: the case of Nande

The Bantu language Nande has an atypical prepositional clitic very similar in most respects with Ju|'hoan *kò*. *Baker & Collins 2006* provide both a detailed description of this aspect of Nande, and a formal analysis aiming at a unified account of this 'linker' and of the atypical prepositions of Khoisan languages. The main differences between Nande and Ju|'hoan are that (a) in a construction involving more than two successive terms in postverbal position, the Nande 'linker' can occur only once, before the second postverbal term, and (b) it agrees in class with the preceding term. But the crucial point is that Nande has possibilities of variations in the linear order of postverbal terms similar to those of Ju|'hoan.

Ex. (38) illustrates this mechanism in a monotransitive construction to which an instrumental satellite (encoded as a locative) is added.

(38) *Nande (Baker & Collins 2006)*

- a. *Kambale moasenyire olukwi l' omo-mbasa*
 1.Kambale AFF.S3:1.TAM.chop 11.wood 11.LK LOC18-9.axe
 'Kambale chopped wood with an axe'
- b. *Kambale moasenyire omo-mbasa m' olukwi*
 1.Kambale AFF.S3:1.TAM.chop LOC18-9.axe 18.LK 11.wood
 'Kambale chopped wood with an axe'

In the particular case of *give* and other verbs with a similar argument structure, this gives rise to a very particular type of double object construction:

- either the recipient precedes the gift, and the gift is introduced by a 'linker' showing class agreement with the recipient,
- or the gift precedes the recipient, and the recipient is introduced by a 'linker' showing class agreement with the gift – ex. (39).¹⁹

(39) *Nande (Baker & Collins 2006)*

- a. *Kambale asengera omwami y' ehilanga*
 1.Kambale AFF.S3:1.TAM.pack.APPL 1.chief 1.LK 19.peanuts
 'Kambale packed peanuts for the chief'
- a. *Kambale asengera ehilanga hy' omwami*
 1.Kambale AFF.S3:1.TAM.pack.APPL 19.peanuts 19.LK 1.chief
 'Kambale packed peanuts for the chief'

Note that ex. (38a) alone would be compatible with a 'possessive' interpretation of the type suggested above for Baule, but such an interpretation is incompatible with the possible variation in constituent order, and with the presence of the same 'linker' in constructions that exclude any connection with the notion of possession.

¹⁹ This example illustrates the construction of the applicative form of a monotransitive verb, but Collins explicitly states that *give* behaves in exactly the same way.

To the best of my knowledge, Nande is the only Bantu language in which similar phenomena have been observed, and it is spoken in an area very far from the South African Khoisan area, which excludes any explanation involving contact phenomena.

8.3.4. Atypical prepositions in the construction of give: the case of Lamba

According to *Aritiba 1987*, in the Gur language **Lamba** much in the same way as in Ju|'hoan or Nande, the NPs in the construction of *give* representing the recipient and the gift do not have a fixed order, but the first NP is immediately juxtaposed to the verb, whereas the second one must be introduced by a preposition *ka* in the absence of which the first NP would be interpreted as its genitival modifier – ex. (40).

(40) *Lamba (Aritiba 1987)*

a. *yàl* *há* *hí* *ká* 'úró
 woman.SG give.PF yam.PL *KA* Uro
 'The woman gave yams to Uro'

b. *yàl* *há* *úró* *ká* 'hí
 woman.SG give.PF Uro *KA* yam.PL
 'The woman gave yams to Uro'

recipient-object SOC (=donative)
gift-object SOC (=dative SOC)

This could be analyzed as an alternation between a SOC with the gift in the role of object and a SOC with the recipient in the role of object, with the particularity that the two alternative constructions would involve not only the same verb, but also the same preposition, which would be very unusual, since in languages in which these two types of construction are attested, they do not use the same adposition. But it seems preferable to recognize a DOC of the particular type already encountered in Ju|'hoan and Nande, since *ka* is more generally a 'transparent' preposition with distributional characteristics essentially similar to those of Ju|'hoan *kò*, or of the 'linker' of Nande. It occurs not only in the construction of verbs whose argument structure is similar to that of *give*, but also in a variety of other constructions, and the only constant in its uses is that it never occurs between a verb and a NP, but always between two NPs that are not in a dependent – head relation, and constitute two distinct terms in the construction of the same verb, which led Aritiba to analyze it as a marker of disjunction, and to consider the construction illustrated by ex. (40) as a DOC with a 'disjunctive marker'.

Nothing similar seems to have been reported so far for any other West African language, including among the closest relatives of Lamba.

9. Recipients and beneficiaries

9.1. General remarks on the extension of the construction characteristic of verbs of giving

A complete account of ditransitive alignment should take into consideration, not only the relation between the encoding of giving events and the typical monotransitive construction, but also the extension of the use of constructions identical to the construction of verbs of giving to encode events having more or less affinities with giving events. In this respect, African languages attest situations ranging from cases in which a

construction identical to that of *give* is productively used for the description of a wide variety of types of events, to cases in which the construction of *give* is shared only by a very limited set of verbs (Hausa illustrating the most extreme case, in which no other verb has a construction identical to that of *give* – see section 9.5.3 below).

Verbs of saying are among those frequently mentioned by descriptive grammars as having a construction identical to that of the verbs of giving. This is not surprising, given the affinity between the semantic role of addressee in the argument structure of verbs of saying and the semantic role of recipient in the argument structure of verbs of giving. The assimilation is however not always total. For example, Bambara has the same type of construction for *di* ‘give’ and *fɔ* ‘say’, ‘tell’ but the postposition marking the addressee in the construction of *fɔ* is different from the postposition used to mark the recipient in the construction of *di* – ex. (41).

(41) *Bambara*

a. *Modu ye wari di Seku ma*
 Modou TAM money give Sékou POSTP
 ‘Modou gave money to Sékou’

b. *Modu ye tiyen fɔ Seku ye*
 Modou TAM truth tell money POSTP
 ‘Modou told the truth to Sékou’

A precise investigation of this question should in particular take into account the fact that verbs of saying frequently show lexical distinctions involving variations in their argument structure, as in English *say/tell/speak*, which have no equivalent with verbs of giving.

Verbs of transfer (*bring something somewhere*) are another semantic group of verbs whose construction is interesting to compare with that of verbs of giving, in particular when the role of destination is assigned to an animate referent (*bring something to somebody*), resulting in an argument frame whose affinity with the argument frame of the verbs of giving is obvious. In this connection, it has already been mentioned that, in languages having SOCs of the verbs of giving with the gift in the role of object, the *dative/allative* syncretism is particularly widespread.

It is also well known that the use of a construction identical to that of *give* is among the possible strategies to organize the construction of causative verb forms derived from transitive verbs, the causee being encoded in the same way as the recipient in the construction of the verbs of giving. Causative periphrases such as French *donner quelque chose à faire à quelqu’un* (lit. ‘give something to do to somebody’) provide a semantic explanation of this possible alignment of causative constructions on the construction of *give*.²⁰

The following sections will concentrate on the treatment of beneficiaries. The justification of this restriction is that, on the one hand, a comprehensive investigation of this question would require much more time than I can reasonably consider devoting to it, and on the other hand, given the obvious affinities between the semantic roles of beneficiary and recipient, it is particularly interesting to raise the question of a possible

²⁰ Several languages attest both a causative periphrasis and a benefactive periphrasis involving a verb *give*, the only difference being in the position of *give*: in first position in the causative periphrasis, in second position in the benefactive periphrasis.

relation between the construction of the most basic verbs of giving and the strategies used to encode beneficiaries.

9.2. Beneficiaries in monoverbal constructions in languages in which the verbs of giving have a SOC with the gift in the role of object

In languages in which the most basic verbs of giving have a SOC with the gift in the role of object', beneficiaries are generally added to the construction encoding the event for which a beneficiary is mentioned without necessitating any modification of this construction, and their role is encoded by means of a case affix or adposition.

In some languages, the case affix or adposition marking the recipient in the construction of the most basic verbs of giving can be used to mark beneficiaries too, whereas some other languages necessarily have a different marking for beneficiaries.

For example, Berber languages use the same preposition *i-* for recipients and beneficiaries – ex. (42), and Zarma uses the same postposition for recipients and beneficiaries – ex. (43), whereas in Bambara, the postposition encoding the semantic role of beneficiary (*ye*) is different from that used to mark the recipient in the construction of *di* 'give' (*ma*) – ex. (44).

(42) *Tamazight* (Penchoen 1973)

a. *šan irəyzən θimizaɾ i-θəwθmin*
 give.TAM.S3P man.PL shawl.PL DAT-woman.PL
 'The men gave shawls to the women'

b. *að-isəy bba učči i-iširran*
 TAM.buy.S3SM father food DAT-child.PL
 'Father will buy food for the children'

(43) *Zarma* (Oumarou Yaro 1993)

a. *múúsà nà ɲgà mòótàà nóó káynòó sè*
 Moussa TAM 3S car.DEF give younger brother.DEF DAT
 'Moussa has given his car to his younger brother'

b. *múúsà nà fèèjì wíí yàwòó sè*
 Moussa TAM sheep kill guest.DEF DAT
 'Moussa has killed a sheep for the guest'

(44) *Bambara*

a. *Fatu na sogo dí Seku ma*
 Fatou TAM meat give Sékou to
 'Fatou will give the meat to Sékou'

b. *Fatu na sogo tobi Seku ye*
 Fatou TAM meat cook Sékou for
 'Fatou will cook the meat for Sékou'

In languages in which the dative term in the construction of verbs of giving behaves as an ordinary oblique, NPs representing beneficiaries behave as ordinary obliques too, irrespective of the fact that they are marked by a dative case affix or adposition or by a distinct case affix or adposition. In languages in which datives have core syntactic term properties, if beneficiaries show the same marking as recipients, they generally share with them their core syntactic term properties, but if they show a distinct marking, they do not share the core syntactic term properties of datives.

9.3. Beneficiaries in monoverbal constructions in languages in which the verbs of giving have a DOC

9.3.1. Beneficiaries in the role of object in DOCs licensed by an applicative derivation

In many African languages in which the most basic verbs of giving have a DOC, beneficiaries are commonly encoded as full-blown objects in a DOCs, i.e., in the same way as recipients, with however the difference that the presence of an object NP representing a beneficiary triggers the use of an applicative form of the verb. This strategy, particularly common among Bantu languages, is widely attested in the Atlantic family too (Wolof, Fulfulde, Bijogo etc.). It is also for example attested in the Kru languages Grebo and Wobe, and outside Niger-Congo, in several Nilotic languages.

In Tswana, applicative derivation is necessary, not only to license object NPs encoding beneficiaries, but also to license the presence of NPs representing recipients in the construction of verbs that are not prototypical verbs of giving, such as *kwala* 'write' – ex. (45). This verb is strictly bivalent, and the only way to encode a possible recipient (*write something to somebody*) is to use its applicative form. The same applicative derivation is necessary to license the addition of a beneficiary, and if both a recipient and a beneficiary are mentioned, the derivative suffix must be reduplicated to license a three object construction in which the object that immediately follows the verb must be interpreted as the beneficiary.²¹

(45) *Tswana*

a. *Ke-kwal-a lokwalo*
 S1S-write-FIN 11.letter
 'I'm writing a letter'

b. *Ke-kwal-el-a malome lokwalo*
 S1S-write-APPL-FIN 1.uncle.1S 11.letter
 'I'm writing a letter to my uncle OR on behalf of my uncle'

c. *Ke-kwal-el-el-a mme malome lokwalo*
 S1S-write-APPL-APPL-FIN 1.mother.1S 1.uncle.1S 11.letter
 'I'm writing a letter to my uncle on behalf of my mother'

²¹ Given the general rule of ordering of the objects in the DOCs of Tswana – see section 3.4, the fact that the beneficiary takes precedence over the recipient in the linear order can be viewed as an indirect manifestation of Animacy Hierarchy: beneficiaries are necessarily animates, whereas the semantic role of recipient has clear affinities with the role of destination, typically associated with inanimate rather than animate referents.

Lango is particularly interesting to observe in this connection, since in the construction of the Lango verb *mùyò* 'give', the recipient can be treated, either as an object in a DOC, or as an oblique. In Lango, when a beneficiary is added to the construction of a bivalent verb, it is treated in the same way as the recipient in the DOC of *mùyò* 'give', and the verb takes the applicative form. If a beneficiary is added to the construction of *mùyò* 'give', the recipient cannot appear as an object, and must be encoded as a preposition phrase – ex. (46).²²

(46) *Lango* (Noonan 1992)

- a. *dákò òtèdò rìgò*
 woman S3S.cook.TAM meat
 'The wooman cooked the meat'
- b. *dákò òtèddì lócè rìgò*
 woman S3S.cook.APPL.TAM man meat
 'The wooman cooked the meat for the man'
- c. *lócè òmùyì àtún búk bòt dákò*
 man S3S.give.APPL.TAM child book to woman
 'The man gave the book to the woman for the child'

Ju|'hoan encodes benefactives by means of an applicative construction involving compound verbs.²³ As illustrated by ex. (47), in Ju|'hoan, /'àn 'give' placed immediately after another verb fulfills the same function as applicative suffixes in other languages.

(47) *Ju|'hoan* (Dickens 2005)

- Dshàú n/óá /'àn ha dà'ámá kò 'msì*
 woman cook give 3S son KO child food
 'The woman cooked food for her child'

9.3.2. Beneficiaries in the role of object in DOCs without applicative derivation

A striking characteristic of the Bantu language Eton is the absence of applicative derivation and a particularly wide use of non-derived verb forms in monoverbal constructions involving, in addition to the subject, two or more nominal terms devoid of any overt marking (Van de Velde 2006). In particular, in Eton, recipients and beneficiaries can equally be represented by NPs devoid of any marking, and the presence of a beneficiary devoid of any mark of its role does not trigger the use of a special verb form. Therefore, Eton is an exception to the regularity according to which, in Bantu languages, monoverbal constructions in which a beneficiary is encoded in the same way as the recipient in the construction of *give* must be licensed by an applicative derivation.

²² The fact that the beneficiary takes precedence over the recipient in the selection of the participants encoded as objects can be viewed as a manifestation of Animacy Hierarchy.

²³ Notes that Dickens 2005 misleadingly applies the term 'serial verbs' to combinations of verbs that are clear instances of compounding, since nothing can be inserted between the two verbs, and all non-subject terms follow the block constituted by the two verbs.

Among languages in which the most basic verbs of giving occur in DOCs, the possibility to treat beneficiaries in the role of object in the same way of recipients without encoding the introduction of an additional participant by means of an applicative derivation is attested for example by the Kru language Dida and the Gur language Ncam (Bassar).

9.3.3. Beneficiaries as obliques in languages in which the verbs of giving occur in DOCs

Beneficiaries encoded by means of adposition phrases in languages in which the most basic verbs of giving occur in a DOC are not common, but this strategy is used by the Gur language Gurma (Ouoba 1982).

In Anywa (Reh 1996), beneficiaries can be, either treated as obliques introduced by means of a preposition, or promoted to object of a derived verb form, but only at the expense of the participant treated as the object of the non-derived verb form.

9.4. Beneficiaries in monoverbal constructions in languages in which the verbs of giving have a SOC with the recipient in the role of object

My language sample includes only two languages in which the usual equivalent of *give* has a SOC with the recipient in the role of object', which excludes putting forward generalizations.

In Yoruba, beneficiaries are encoded by means of an applicative periphrasis of the serial type – see section 9.5.1.

=Hoan, like Ju|'hoan (see section 9.3.1), uses compound verbs whose second element is *cu* 'give'. In the construction of these compound verbs, in =Hoan, the beneficiary is treated as the direct object, exactly like the recipient in the construction of *cu*, and if the first element of the compound verb is a transitive verb, its object is demoted to oblique (in other words, it is treated like the gift in the construction of *cu*) – ex. (48), to compare with ex. (36) above.

(48) =Hoan (Collins 2003)

Ma 'a tsaxo cu Jefa ki //a"e
1s PROG cook give Jeff KI meat
'I am cooking meat for Jeff'

9.5. Applicative periphrases

In some languages, the mention of a beneficiary triggers the use of an applicative periphrasis.

Applicative periphrases are complex predicates superficially identical to clause chains typically used to encode sequences of events, in which the verb encoding the event for which an additional participant is mentioned combines with another verb in the function of valency operator.

In applicative periphrases used to introduce the mention of a beneficiary, the verb encoding the event always occurs in first position, followed by the verb *give* with the NP representing the beneficiary as its complement. The use of this strategy does not seem to correlate with any of the basic types of ditransitive alignment.

Formally, three types of such periphrases must be distinguished, depending on the formal types of clause chains whose grammaticalization can result in the emergence of such complex predicates.

9.5.1. The serial type

In the serial type, the complex predicate is devoid of any overt evidence of a hierarchical relation between its two elements, in the sense that none of them bears any overt mark identifying it as a dependent verb form. Ex. (49) from Yoruba illustrates this type of applicative periphrasis, common in the serializing languages of West Africa (Kwa and Western Benue-Congo languages).

(49) *Yoruba*

Òjò rà iwé fún iyá
Ojo buy book give mother
'Ojo bought a book for his mother'

In ex. (50) from Igbo, the first occurrence of *nyé* 'give' encodes the event 'give' with its three arguments, and the second occurrence introduces an additional participial in the role of beneficiary.

(50) *Igbo*

ó nyèrè m̀ jí 'nyé 'úbá
S3S give.PF O1S yam give Uba
'He gave me yams for Uba'

The same type of periphrasis is often used also with verbs of giving other than the most basic ones. For example, in Kposo, *uyè* 'lend' occurs in a construction of this type, in which its recipient is introduced by *ká* 'give' – ex. (51).

(51) *Kposo (Eklo 1987)*

kúmá á-uyè ègà ká kòkú
Kuma S3S-lend money give Koku
'Kuma lent money to Koku'

Outside the area of West Africa characterized by a particular concentration of languages having very productive serial constructions with a variety of semantic functions, applicative periphrases of the serial type are also used to introduce beneficiaries in the Gur language Kasim (*Bonvini 1988*), in the Ubangian language Ngbandi (*Toronzoni 1989*), and in the Sara (Central Sudanic) languages Kabba (*Moser 2005*) and Sar (*Palayer 1989*).

9.5.2. The type with an independent verb form in first position

In the other two types of applicative periphrases used to introduce beneficiaries, one of the two verbs constituting a complex predicate is in a non-autonomous form typically encountered also in clause chains encoding sequences of events.

In the type illustrated by the Grassfields Bantu language Mankon – ex. (52), the first verb (i.e., the verb encoding the event for which a beneficiary is mentioned) is in an independent form, and *give* is in the sequential form. The presence of this type of

periphrasis in Mankon is quite obviously conditioned by the fact that clause chains with a finite verb form in the first clause only are typical of Bantu languages. Note that, by contrast, Mankon is not a typical Bantu language in having a SOC with the gift in the role of object (and not a DOC) for the verb *give*.

(52) *Mankon* (Leroy 2003)

mà mʔí fàʔá ɣʔá mbó zúó
 1S TAM work SEQ.give to 1S.ENUNC
 'I shall work for him'

The Cross River language Obolo provides another example of this type of applicative periphrasis – see Rowland-Oke 2003.

9.5.3. The type with an independent verb form in second position

The 3rd type, with *give* in an independent form and the verb encoding the event in a form of the type commonly called converb, is typical of SOV languages having clause chains in which the last clause only is finite. Outside Africa, it is attested for example in Mongolian, and in Tamil. Among African languages, it is not very common, but the Saharan language Beria – ex. (53) – provides an illustration, and it is found also in Ijo (Williamson 1965).

(53) *Beria* (Jakobi & Crass 2004)

áská gí-n-é é-géí
 door open-S2S-CONV O1S-give.TAM
 'Open the door for me' (lit. 'Having opened the door give me')

Note that the first two types of applicative periphrases (but not the third one) can very easily lead to the grammaticalization of a form of the verb *give* as a benefactive adposition.

9.6. Atypical or problematic cases

9.6.1. Kanuri

The Kanuri verbs of giving have a SOC with the gift in the role of object. Beneficiaries are encoded by NPs in the dative case, which is quite usual, but dative NPs representing beneficiaries must be licensed by a valency increasing derivation – ex. (54), which is cross-linguistically not common.²⁴

(54) *Kanuri* (Cyffer, 1991)

a. Bíntu béri déwono
 Bintu food cook.TAM.S3S
 'Bintu will cook food'

²⁴ Outside Africa, a similar treatment of beneficiaries is however found in Georgian, and in North West Caucasian languages.

- a. *Bintu am-nzə-ro bəri déjwo*
 Bintu person-3S-DAT food cook.APPL.TAM.S3S
 'Bintu will cook food for her people'

9.6.2. Amharic

The Amharic verbs of giving have a SOC with the gift in the role of object, with the particularity that recipients, in spite of their dative marking, can be indexed on the verb exactly in the same way as monotransitive patients encoded by NPs in the absolute form or in the accusative case. Beneficiaries are usually encoded by NPs showing the same dative marking as beneficiaries, but, contrary to recipients, they obey the general rule according to which, in Amharic, verb suffixes identical to object markers can be used to pronominalize NPs marked by one of the two prepositional clitics *bä-* and *lä-*, but only if the object marker is preceded by one of the suffixes *-bb-* and *-ll-*, obviously cognate with the corresponding prepositions, and synchronically analyzable as applicative suffixes with somewhat atypical properties – ex. (55).

(55) *Amharic* (Cohen 1970, Appleyard 1995)

- a. *Bunna afäll-u*
 coffee boil.TAM-S3P
 'They boiled coffee'
- b. *Bunna lä-gwadännä-ččäw afäll-u*
 coffee DAT-friend-3P boil.TAM-S3P
 'They boiled coffee for their friend'
- c. *Bunna afäll-u-lli-n*
 coffee boil.TAM-S3P-APPL-O1P
 'They boiled coffee for us'

In addition to that, *Amberber 2000* mentions the possibility to encode participants normally marked with one of the two prepositional clitics *bä-* and *lä-* as direct objects marked by the accusative suffix *-n*, on condition that the verb includes an applicative suffix and an object marker coreferent with the NP in the accusative case, as in ex. (56).

(56) *Amharic* (Amberber 2000)

- a. *Aster-in färräd-ä-ll-at*
 Aster-ACC judge.TAM-S3SM-APPL-O3SF
 'He judged in Aster's favor' (i.e., he acquitted her)

9.6.3. Hausa

The Hausa verb *baà* 'give' occurs in a double object construction in which the recipient is treated exactly in the same way as the monotransitive patient, which is quite exceptional for a Chadic language – ex. (57).

(57) *Hausa*

a. *Yaa baà Audù àbinci*
 s3SM.TAM give Audu food
 'He gave food to Audu'

b. *Yaa baa-nì àbinci*
 s3SM.TAM give-O1S food
 'He gave me food'

But in Hausa, the other verbs of giving, as well as verbs of saying, and verbs of transfer in constructions involving a recipient, have a single object construction in which a prepositional phrase representing the recipient is inserted between the verb and the object, and the same preposition is used to encode beneficiaries – ex. (58).

(58) *Hausa*

a. *Yaa kaawoo wà Audù àbinci*
 s3SM.TAM bring to Audu food
 'He brought food to Audu'

b. *Yaa yii wà sarkii aikii*
 s3SM.TAM do to chief work
 'He worked for the chief'

In *SVO* languages in which objects are devoid of any marking, it is not common for transitive verbs to be obligatorily separated from their object by a prepositional phrase representing a non-essential term. In particular, in Chadic languages, the general rule is that non-pronominalized datives are preposition phrases that obligatorily follow unmarked NPs in object role.

This suggests reanalyzing the preposition involved in this construction of Hausa as a verbal suffix similar to the applicative extension of Bantu verbs, which would lead to recognize in Hausa the kind of situation commonly found in African languages in which the most basic verbs of giving have a double object construction, with only a particularly wide use of applicative derivation $\cancel{X}$ license DOCs. But *Newman 2000* argues in favour of the traditional treatment and provides some evidence against the analysis of *wà* as a verbal suffix.

According to *Newman 1982*, the explanation of this exceptional pattern of Hausa is a reinterpretation of possessives as datives, but some details of the scenario he puts forward are not entirely clear.

9.6.4. *Somali*

In the Cushitic language Somali, verbs of giving have a DOC, and the mention of a beneficiary trigger the presence of the 'preposition' *ú*. But this 'preposition' belongs to a paradigm of 4 units with properties that crucially differ from words or clitics commonly identified as prepositions "in not being next to the noun they govern but placed before the verb, regardless of the position of their noun" (*Saeed 1987:185*). In spite of the fact that they are not morphologically attached to the verb, the fixed position of these prepositions within the 'verbal piece' (*Saeed 1987:200*) suggests that they should better be analyzed as valency operators licensing the use of non-arguments in the role of object, functionally similar to the applicative suffixes of Bantu languages.

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Abbreviations used in the glosses

In Bantu examples, numbers preceding the glosses of nominal forms indicate the class to which they belong.

1S	1st person singular
2S	2nd person singular
3S	3rd person singular
3SM	3rd person singular masculine
1P	1st person plural
2P	2nd person plural
3P	3rd person plural
3:X	(in Bantu examples) 3rd person class X
ABS	absolutive
ACC	accusative
AFF	affirmative
ALL	allative
APPL	applicative
AUX	auxiliary
CONV	converb
D	dative object marker
DAT	dative
DECL	declarative
DEF	definite
DEM	demonstrative
ENUNC	enunciative marker
ERG	ergative
FIN	final (in Bantu verb morphology, a final vowel whose variations contribute to the identification of the grammatical value of the verb)
FOC	focalization

FUT	future
IPF	imperfective
LK	linker
NEG	negation
O	object marker
O'	restricted object marker
OBL	oblique
PASS	passive
PF	perfective
PL	plural
POSTP	postposition
PREP	preposition
PRO	personal pronoun
PROG	progressive
S	subject marker
SEQ	sequential
SG	singular
TAM	tense-aspect-mood marker
VFOC	verb focalization

Annex: The construction of the equivalents of give in a sample of African languages

In addition to the languages mentioned in the text, this list includes other languages for which data illustrating the construction of an equivalent of *give* in its basic meaning were available.

(abbreviations: DOC = double object construction, SOC/G = single object construction with the gift in the role of object, SOC/R = single object construction with the recipient in the role of object, TGC = *take ... give* construction)

Afroasiatic

Semitic

Moroccan Arabic: SOC/G

Ge'ez: SOC/G

Amharic: SOC/G

Zay: SOC/G

Berber

Tamazight: SOC/G

Kabyle: SOC/G

Egyptian

all stages in the history of Ancient Egyptian, from Old Egyptian to Coptic: SOC/G

Cushitic

Somali: DOC

Dhaasanac: DOC

Oromo: SOC/G

Dullay: SOC/G

Ts'amakko: SOC/G

K'abena: SOC/G

Kambaata: SOC/G

Omotic

Maale: SOC/G

Chadic

Hausa: DOC

Kanakuru: SOC/G

Ngamo: SOC/G

Kera: SOC/G

Dangaleat: SOC/G

Tera: SOC/G

Ngizim: SOC/G

Pero: SOC/G

Nilo-Saharan

Songhay

Gao Songhay: SOC/G, DOC

Zarma: SOC/G

Saharan

Kanuri: SOC/G

Beria: DOC, SOC/G

Kuliak

Ik: SOC/G

Maban

—

Fur

—

Central Sudanic

Kabba: DOC

Sar: DOC

Ngiti: SOC/G

Berta

—

Kunama (isolated N.S. language): SOC/G?

East Sudanic (including Nilotic)

Turkana: DOC

Anywa: DOC

Dinka: DOC

Koman

—

Gumuz

—

Kadu

Krongo: SOC/G

Niger-Congo

Kordofanian

—

Atlantic

Wolof: DOC

Fulfulde: DOC

Serer: DOC
Noon: DOC
Diola-Banjai: DOC
Diola-Fogny: DOC
Bijogo: DOC

Mande

Manding (Bambara, Maninka, etc.): SOC/G, SOC/R
Soso: SOC/G, SOC/R
Mende: SOC/G, SOC/R
Kpelle: SOC/G, SOC/R
Soninke: SOC/G
Dan: SOC/G
Guro: SOC/G
Bisa: SOC/G
Bobo: SOC/G
San: SOC/G

Gur

Lamba: DOC
Dagbani: DOC
Pana: SOC/G
Gurma: DOC
Ncam (Bassar): DOC
Moore: DOC
Koromfe: DOC

Kru

Grebo: DOC
Wobe: DOC
Neyo: DOC
Bete: DOC
Lakota Dida: DOC

Kwa

Ega: DOC
Adioukrou: DOC
Attie: DOC, TGC
Ebrie: DOC
Baule: DOC, TGC
Ewe: DOC, TGC
Fon: DOC, TGC
Kposo: DOC, TGC
Igo: DOC, TGC

Adamawa

Samba Leko: DOC
Tupuri: SOC/G

Ubangian

Gbeya: SOC/G
Banda-Linda: SOC/G
Mono: SOC/G
Ngbandi: DOC

Benue-Congo (including Bantu)

Yoruba: SOC/R, TGC

Fyem: DOC
Urhobo: DOC
Igbo: DOC
Kana: DOC
Obolo: DOC
Tiv: DOC
Degema: DOC, SOC/G
Mankon: SOC/G
Aghem: SOC/G
(Narrow Bantu) Eton: DOC, Chaga: DOC, Haya: DOC, Nande: DOC Swahili:
DOC, Shimaore: DOC, Kinyarwanda: DOC, Ngangela: DOC, Chewa: DOC,
Tswana: DOC, Sotho: DOC, Xhosa: DOC, Zulu: DOC, etc.

Ijo

Kolokuma Ijo: TGC

Dogon

Jamsay: SOC/G

Pre (isolated N.C. languages): SOC/G

Khoisan

Khoe

Khoekhoe (Nama): DOC

Non-Khoe South African Khoisan

Ju|'hoan: DOC

N|uu: SOC/G

=Hoan: SOC/R

East African Khoisan

References for the annex

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